

Impact of Diversification on Household Food Security: A Study of Northern Bihar

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the impact of diversification towards high value crops on household food security. This is a micro-level study based on primary survey in the northern Bihar. The high value crops are income augmenting and the increased income by allocating more resources can have a favorable impact on the household's food security. The analysis is carried out for diversification in terms of land allocation towards high value crops and also in terms of the diversity in allocation among various crops at the household level. The results indicate that diversification improves the household's food security. High value crops being income augmenting and labour intensive supplements the household income and enhances the food security. The analysis also reveals that the diversification in terms of multiple cropping that leads to a diversified crop portfolio does not have an adverse impact on household food security.

KEYWORDS: Agricultural Diversification, High Value Crops, Food Security,
JEL: Q00, Q13, Q16, Q18

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of agriculture diversification emerged from the allocation of resources among multiple crops so as to minimize the risk of crop failure and market risk and food security was an important aspect of this strategy. But later on diversification assumed multi-dimensional importance ranging from reducing the risk, augment the farm income to achieving the food security. However in recent decades, diversification has emerged as more resource allocation for high value crops having high returns. The rationale is that income generated from high value crops can augment the household income for food and other requirements. (Goletti, 1999; Fafchamps, 1992; Govereh and Jayne, 2003; Von Braun, 1994). Further, it increases the total crop productivity, reduces the risk associated with monocropping and stabilizes the farm income and generated employment opportunities in rural areas (Hyami and Otsuka, 1995). It is also suggested that allocation of more resources for high value crops will make the agriculture competitive at international level and help to cope up with the challenges arising out of globalization and liberalization (Radhakrishna and Reddy, 2004).

But the assumption underlying the strategy of diversification in favour of high value crops is that the household's food security will be maintained by the exchange of commodities in the market. But for every commodity produced or needed, there may be non-existent or non-competitive. For food security, the household cannot rely on markets and may prefer to be food self-sufficient instead of higher returns from high value crops (Pingali and Rosegrant, 1995; Delgado and Siamwalla, 1997). Not only the existence and efficiency of markets, the diversification decisions are influenced by a number of factors, including the level of infrastructure development and household's food security. Households that have the food security concerns and don't want to take risk may prioritize to have food self-sufficiency.

The literature on diversification highlights various aspects and interrelations among several variables that influence the diversification. Some of the studies maintain that while diversification increases income of household by creating employment opportunities and improving the productivity of labour, the household food security is not adversely affected (Govereh and Jayne, 2003; Von Braun, 1995;). Rather the income generated improves the consumption and food security (Minot et al., 2006; Joshi et al., 2003; Windle and Rolfe, 2005). But there are studies that have highlighted the concerns. In developing countries households allocate significant resources to subsistence crops to maintain food security and then diversify (Jayne, 1994; Joshi et al. 2003). The dependence on market may have adverse impact on the food security. The inefficient markets and price instability may deteriorate

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the household's food security (Thomson & Metz, 1998) and households may not rely on markets for food security (Delgado and Siamwalla, 1997).

Agriculture Diversification and Food Security in India: Historical and Policy Context

The Indian economy has experienced several changes in its agricultural development policies with Green Revolution and Economic Reforms being the most significant. In the immediate post-Independence period, the returns from agriculture were highly inconsistent and economy faced the severe food security crisis. The Government of India therefore, launched various development programmes, actively pursued tremendous agrarian reforms, institutional and technological changes to increase the agriculture production. The Planning Commission also laid emphasis on increasing agricultural production, generating employment opportunities and reducing the inequality of incomes in the rural sector. Agriculture sector was given the highest priority during the First Five Year Plan (1951-56) to tide over the difficult food problems and at this stage, agriculture diversification was primarily viewed as state-led diversification with achievement of food self-sufficiency as its prime objective. However, despite all these measures, food security situation remained bleak and the country remained dependent on imports for feeding its population.

The new agriculture strategy popularly known as "Green Revolution" proved to be the most important step towards the change in cropping pattern and improvement in the food security. Under the new strategy the main focus was on the use of high-yielding varieties of seeds, multiple cropping, widespread use of irrigation facilities and use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides. The prime concern of policy makers during this period was to carry on research and development in agriculture sector, input supply, price support and spread of technology etc. However, the strategy was confined to high yielding varieties of few crops in selected areas. At this stage, agriculture diversification was viewed as a means to reduce the risk, improve the food security and increase the growth in agriculture sector of the economy. The new agricultural policy successfully achieved the food self-sufficiency and improved the growth of agriculture sector (Hazra, 2003). With the special emphasis on agriculture development, the economy experienced with steady increase in area under cultivation and rise in agricultural productivity.

Pursuing the self-sufficiency goal, the Cropping patterns for a long time remained confined to the production of food grains with very few regions devoting some resources to commercial crops. In the post trade liberalization and globalization period, the changes in pattern of domestic demand, huge surplus of food grain and export demand led to changes in resource use and diversification towards high value crops. Thus lately, diversification of agriculture in favour of more competitive and high value commodities emerged as a significant strategy to overcome the emerging challenges of globalization and as a source of growth in agriculture sector (Joshi et al. 2002). The diversification towards high value crops emerged as the most important source of agricultural growth both during 1980s and 1990s. The agriculture sector witnessed a sharp change in cropping pattern, increasing the share of high value crops such as oilseeds, horticultural crops, spices and sugarcane in gross-cropped area (Joshi et.al, 2004). The relative prices of the crops were the main driving force for changes in cropping pattern. Whereas the price of rice and wheat, covered under Minimum Support Price policy of the government were consistently increased in order to protect the interests of the farmers. On the other hand, globalization and liberalization and the changing consumption patterns increased the demand for wide varieties of high value agricultural crops and created new prospects for farmers to produce and export to global markets. Thus agriculture diversification emerged as a strategy to stabilize and increase the farm income, generate employment opportunities and accelerate the growth in agriculture sector (Vyas, 1996 and Joshi, 2007).

Since independence, the agricultural development in India has focused on Food security. Huge imports of food grains particularly during the mid-1960s had raised the concern for food security and food self-sufficiency. The regular food import was recognized as undesirable strategy to meet the food needs (Shergill, 2011). for a long time this focus remained on the self-sufficiency, and the cropping patterns in India was dominated by the food grain production. during the 1970s and 1980s, the green revolution technology the high yielding varieties especially of rice and wheat, resulted in a steady growth rate of food grain production that increased the agricultural growth and incomes. The diversification towards high value commodities has emerged as an important source of growth in agriculture and rural income generation. The diversification along with the urbanization have improved food and nutritional security thereby increasing the diversification and increasing farm income and access to food. With rise in income, the consumers have wider choice of foods resulting in changes in their dietary pattern.

II. DATA SOURCE AND METHODOLOGY

Having discussed the diversification and food security issues and concerns in general and specific to the Indian context this study pertains to the northern region of Bihar. Considering the various studies for highlighting the benefits of land allocation towards high value crops, studies highlighting the concerns for food security and role of various factors, this study aims to address the impact of diversification towards high value crops on household food security. We will also try to figure whether allocation of land among competing crops at household level has any impact on the food security. Generally the rural markets are incomplete

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or inefficient. We hypothesize that diversification towards high value crop would have adverse impact on household food security. We also hypothesize that multiple cropping at farm level does not impact household food security.

Hypothesis I:

H₀: Diversification towards high value crop has an adverse impact on household food security.

H₁: Diversification towards high value crop does not have an adverse impact on household food security.

Hypothesis II:

H₀: Multiple cropping at farm level has adverse impact on household food security.

H₁: Multiple cropping at farm level does not have an adverse impact on household food security.

Analytical Framework of the Study

To address these research questions an analytical framework is developed. The Diversification towards high value crops are taken at household level. To analyze the role of diversification on food security we an analytical framework to study these inter-relations between variables taking into consideration the household production and consumption requirements.

Let P be the staple crop production

Then $P = P(x) + e_1$ ----- (I)

Where X represents all variables that impact the production decisions

Let \hat{P} is the estimated production of staple crops

H_{fss} is an estimate of the food self-sufficiency of household

Then $H_{fss} = \hat{P} + F_s - C_r$

Where F_s is food stock at pre-harvest period

C_r is household consumption requirements of food staple

If Y is the land share of the cash crops

$Y = Y(X, H_{fss}) + e_2$ ----- (II)

For null hypothesis, assuming that H_{fss} does not have any significant influence on decisions of diversification towards high value crops, then these terms will have a value that significantly differs from zero. That implies diversification into cash crops will not have adverse impact on household's food security condition. We can specify the model for land allocation towards high value crops for household j, as

$Y_j = X_j\beta + v_j$ ----- (III)

Where,

Y is jth household's land allocated towards high value crops

X is represents all explanatory variables

β is the vector of coefficients associated with the explanatory variables vector X, and

v is the composite error term

The household's food security status is determined by the food entitlements and needs, as given by Thomson and Metz (1998). The household's that have food entitlements greater than their needs are classified as food secure. Whereas the household having entitlements less than their needs are classified as food insecure. The FAO's rule of 200 kg of refined cereal equivalent per capita per annum is used to estimate the food self-sufficiency requirements of the household, taking into consideration the household's size. For determining the food entitlements the household's food expenditure as a percentage of income and household's own production are taken into account.

Let F_N represents the food needs of household and F_E represents the entitlements, H_P be the households own production, and H_Z be Household's family size: then

$F_N = 200 * H_z$

Gap in food security is given by F_N - H_P. For a household to be food secure the gap should be met by the expenditure from the income of the household.

Since food expenditure of an average rural Indian household's is around 53 percent of household consumption expenditure¹. If the share of household's income on food expenditure meets the gap in food security, then the household is classified as food secure. If the expenditure on food is less than the gap, then household falls into the category of food insecure households.

Profile of the Study Area

The study pertains to the northern area of Bihar, with Darbhanga district at the Centre. The area has an agrarian economy and agriculture is the primary occupation of the people. It has vast alluvial plains devoid of hills and highly calcareous soil. The land is very fertile and a mixture of clay & sand makes it suitable for variety of crops. While as Paddy is the main crop, other crops

¹ <https://www.business-standard.com/article/economy-policy/rural-india-tops-consumption-charts-114040300969-1.html>

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being cultivated are wheat, maize, pulses, oil seeds, sugarcane and Maruwa. The district is famous for mango and is the top producer. The other fruit crops are litchi, Pipal, Sisoo, Khajur, Jackfruit, Khair, Palm, Jamun, Guava trees etc. It is also one of the leading fish producing districts in Bihar. The Table 1 below presents the socio-economic and demographic features of the district.

Table 1: Socio-economic and demographic profile of Darbhanga district

Population Census 2011	3921971	Geographic coordinates	Latitude: 25°53' to 26° 27' North
Population density	1101 per sq. km		Longitude: 85°45 to 86° 25 East
Population growth	19%	Temperature	43° C (Max.) 9° C (Min.)
Sex ratio	911 per 1000 male	Average rainfall	1143 mm
Literacy rate	56.56%	Area	2297 sq. km
Languages spoken	Maithili, Hindi and Urdu	Height above sea level	52 meters
Total workers	1,223,640	Per Capita GDP	Rs 15870
Agricultural land labourers	301,524	Total Cultivators	179,408

Source: Census 2011 and Survey GoB

The study is based on primary household survey conducted in four Blocks. The survey area was chosen based on the centrality and prime agriculture belt in the district and in consultation with local district level officers. The Blocks include Benipur, Alinagar, Ghnashampur and Tardi. Then 100 farm agriculture households from each of the selected block were selected forming a sample of around 400 farm households for the study. Before going to the field survey, the various issues agricultural and farm related issues of the study area were thoroughly examined and consultation were held with the block/village level agriculture officers. After getting sufficient understanding, field trips were made to the sample blocks to ground level information about various aspects related to farmers land allocation decision, public distribution system (PDS) related to food security and infrastructure and availability of markets for purchase of farm inputs and sale of the produce. After getting insights from these interactions a structured questionnaire was developed from carrying out primary survey. The questionnaire was framed taking into consideration the key objectives.. The primary activities of the selected households are farm based activities including the livestock production. other than the income from farm produce, the wage income is a significant proportion of the gross income of household's. The process was repeated in each block for a sample size of 100. Thus 400 samples were collected from 4 selected blocks.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Measurement of Key Variables

The main variables are agriculture diversification, Food Security Level, Area under High value crops, Non-farm income, and Diversification index and food security. Based on the research objectives and with given methodology in the analytical framework, we first estimate the food self-sufficiency of individual households. The rice and wheat being the two main cereals produced in the area, they wheat is converted into rice equivalent based on the milling ratios and energy calories derived.

Crop	Calories/kg	Milling ratio	Rice equivalent
Rice	3450	0.65	1
Wheat	3460	0.75	0.997

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of various variables used in the analysis

Variable	Combined	
	Mean	St.Dev
Total cultivated area (in katha)	69.18	28.30
Area under non-staples	26.89	14.31
Food self-sufficiency (1 = food self-sufficient)	0.66	0.43
Food security (1=food secure)	0.95	0.16
Percentage share of non-farm income in total income	61.34	16.82

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Distance to an all-weather road (km)	3.09	0.31
Distance to main market outside Village	4.75	0.35
Credit access (1 = Yes)	0.32	0.13
Sex of farm manager (1 = male)	0.96	0.12
Household size	5.89	2.69
Land rights measure (1= yes)	0.96	0.13
Age of farm manager	50.27	7.96
Education level (Schooling years of farm manager)	6.14	2.65
Marketing cost (Rs/quintal/km)	41	0.36
Dependency ratio	0.33	0.11
Family Labour	1.81	0.98

Source: Primary Survey Data

The Table 2 presents the statistics of various variables in the analysis. First we have calculated the Food Self-sufficiency status of households and then assessed the land allocation of these household by Self-sufficiency status and performed a two sample t-test on the data. The food self-sufficiency is measured as the gap between household's annual food production and consumption requirements. The annual consumption requirements of households are measured by the FAO's rule of 200 kg of refined cereal equivalent per person per annum. If the production meets or exceeds the consumption requirements, the household is food self-sufficient, else it is food deficient. The analysis of the data is given in Table 3.

Table 3: land allocations to high value crops by the households Food self-sufficiency status

Percentage share of land of the high value crops

Food Deficient	Food Self-sufficient	t-statistic
17.79(6.12)	31.24(11.39)	3.08*

*Significant at 1% level, (Fig. in parenthesis is standard deviation)

Table 4: The Food security and self-sufficiency of Households (percentage).

Households	Households (%)
Food Self Sufficient	68
Food Deficient	32
Food Insecure	05
Food Secure	95
Chronic Food Deficient*	15

* Households with own production less than 50% of their requirement

The figure in Table 4 above reveals that the food secure households are in greater percentage than the food self-sufficient households. Since while assessing the food security of households the income from other source is also taken into account. It implies that the non-farm sources have significant proportion in the income of the households that provides for food expenditure and makes them food secure. The share of non-farm income is 51.10 percent. The non-farm income improves food security and helps to meet the food requirements of the household.

The Food Security Level is measured as a percentage of food security gap to total household's consumption requirements. The variable 'Food Security Level' provides an estimate of household's food security status. We use this variable to assess the impact of diversification on household food security. In the regression analysis, to test the hypothesis I, the Food Security Level is taken as dependent variable and 'Area under high value crops' as one of the independent variables. The household's income plays an important role in determining the Food Security Level; all the figures are converted into monetary terms for comparative analysis. The Food Security Level is derived from the food security gap. Since the food security gap is the difference between household's production and consumption requirements, the household's income plays an important role in determining the food security status. If the proportion of household's income that is used for food expenditure meets the food security gap, the household is

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food secure. If the proportion of household's income that is used for food expenditure is less than the food security gap, the household is categorized as food insecure. So the sign and magnitude of 'Food security gap' indicates the level of food security or insecurity. A negative sign of food security gap implies that household is food insecure and vice versa.

To assess the level of multiple cropping we use Simpson Index of diversification (SID). The SID is given by:

$$SID = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i)^2$$

Where, P_i is the proportionate area of the i^{th} crop in gross cultivated area.

To test this hypothesis I and II, we use regression analysis with 'Food Security Level' as dependent variable and Area under high value crops and SID as the independent variables.

The regression equation is specified as:

$$F_{SL} = f(A_{HVC}; NF_i; DPN; F_{LBR}; C_{IN}; SID)$$

Where,

F_{SL} - Food Security Level

A_{HVC} - Area under High value crops

NF_i - Non-farm income (salary etc.)

DPN - Dependency Ratio

F_{LBR} - Family Labour (Adult members involved in agri-activities)

C_{IN} - Cropping intensity

SID - Simpson Index of Diversification

The hypothesis I and II are tested for data in both category of households and the combined data also.

Regression analysis results for households

Table 5 presents the analysis of data obtained from households.

ANOVA and Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	F	Sig.
.879	.778	.673	29.1274	41.341	.000

Table 6: Factors Determining Household Food Security

F_{SL} (Dependent Variable)	Coefficient	t-Values
Constant	-171.632	-6.897*
Area under High value crops	3.217	9.821*
Non- farm Income	.685	8.179*
Dependency ratio	-.219	-.416
Family Labour	1.792	2.912
Cropping intensity	2.165	3.892**
Simpson Index of Diversification	2.658	5.983*

Source: primary survey data

* 1% level of significance; ** 5% level of significance; N = 400

The analysis of data from Table 6 reveals that the coefficient of variable 'Area under High value crops' is positive and is significant at 1% level of significance, implying that diversification towards high value crops has favorable impact on food security of the households. Therefore the Null hypothesis that the diversification towards high value crop has an adverse impact on household food security is rejected. High value crops are income augmenting and labour intensive. This income supplements the household income and enhances the food security. The results of the study are in conformity with the literature that diversification improves the household's food security and facilitates increases in income of household by creating employment opportunities and improving the productivity of labour. (Govere and Jayne, 2003; Von Braun, 1995;). The literature suggests that households while diversifying towards high value crops maintain some area under staple crops to safe guard the self-sufficiency and shields from price fluctuations and market volatility. The income generated improves the consumption and food security (Minot et al., 2006; Joshi et al., 2003; Windle and Rolfe, 2005).

The analysis also reveals that the Simpson Index of Diversification that measures diversification in terms of multiple cropping with positive coefficient, is significant at 1% Level of significance. Therefore the diversified crop portfolio does not have an adverse impact on household food security. The null hypothesis II is rejected. The diversified cropping safeguards the households from risk

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in price volatility, crop failure and provides income stability. The findings are consistent with the literature that agriculture diversification stabilize and increase the farm income, generate employment opportunities and accelerate the growth in agriculture sector (Vyas, 1996 and Joshi, 2007). The other variables of significance are non-farm income and cropping intensity. The variable 'Non-farm income' as expected has positive coefficient and is significant. The non-farm income plays an important role in household's food security. The non-farm sources of income augments farm income and help the households to attain food security. While as the non-farm sources of income are more significant to food deficient households, it helps the households to diversify their consumption basket. The variable 'Dependency ratio' as expected has a negative coefficient, but is not significant. The variable 'Family labour' that is expected to favour the diversification and the household food security, has a positive coefficient but is not significant. The income from the family labour safeguards household's food security. The variable 'cropping intensity' is significant implying that the higher cropping intensity has favorable impact on household's food security.

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